

Junior High School Students Practices on Core Values in One Private Catholic Schools in Leyte

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ABSTRACT

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data on the respondents' level of awareness and extent of practice of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception (FCIC) core values. It also aimed to determine the significant relationship between awareness and practice, the significant differences in how these values are practiced, and the proposed output of the study. A quantitative research design was employed to assess the extent to which FCIC Junior High School students practice the core values. The study included 85 respondents, and statistical tools such as weighted mean and Chi-square tests were used to analyze the data. The survey findings indicate that all five key values—compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship—were well recognized by the respondents. However, in terms of application, students reported that they only fairly practiced these values. This suggests that while awareness of the core values is high, their consistent application in daily life remains an area for improvement. Further analysis revealed a direct relationship between awareness and practice, meaning that higher awareness of these values correlates with greater adherence to them in practice. The respondents demonstrated a moderate level of understanding and application of the core values, indicating room for further reinforcement. These findings emphasize that while students are generally aware of the FCIC core values and apply them to some extent, additional efforts are needed to enhance their practice. Strengthening the integration of these values in both academic and extracurricular activities could foster deeper internalization, thereby contributing to students' personal growth, ethical decision-making, and overall academic development.

Keywords: *core values, compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, responsible stewardship*

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INTRODUCTION

Catholic schools are responsible for the human formation of youth. They are established to create for the school community a special atmosphere brought to life by the spirit of freedom and charity. Catholic schools are set up to help them lead exemplary life of moral virtues. By doing this, the youth will become an agent of change for the betterment of society (Kuehn 2022).

Likewise, in relation to values formation and Vatican Council's emphasis of integrating values in the educational ministry, the core values of an organization form the foundation on which individuals perform work and conduct themselves (Kirova, 2021). Furthermore, he added that core values are the basic elements of how people go about their work and relationships. (Jackson, 2020) asserts that core values are set of beliefs and commitments on how people treat each other. It defines an organization and reflects their collective, and fundamental beliefs.

FCIC as a Catholic school, envision to be Christ-centered, academically innovative, and socially responsive community, committed to evangelizing and witnessing the Gospel values toward the realization of the fullness of life (FCI C Manual, 2017). With the vision of FCIC, it aligns itself with the educational aim of education as a lifelong journey towards the holistic development of the learners from kindergarten until college. Significantly, it transforms individuals intellectually, socially, and psychologically. Nevertheless, it does not only nurture the mind and the body as education aims to develop the spiritual aspect which is nonmaterial, sacred, and with value. Spiritual formation does not happen immediately but it involves a long process and it takes a corroborated effort of the home, school, and community to achieve the ultimate aim.

Moreover, Keiling (2022) concludes that core values serve as a code of conduct and guide individual behaviors throughout all ranks of the organization and drive cultural change, help address unacceptable behavior in a non-threatening way and reinforce desired behaviors. In contention to student's identity, Franchi (2018) singly emphasizes the first dimension of a Catholic School, its Catholic Identity and Mission which reflects on the school's philosophy, vision-mission, and core values. Thus, the Catholic quality of a Catholic School is its reference to a Christian concept of life centered on Jesus Christ as the foundation of the whole educational enterprise. An excellent Catholic school is animated and driven by a philosophy, vision, mission, and core values that embrace and preserve its Catholic identity.

With the core values institutionalized by FCIC, every student is encouraged to embrace and put into practice the core values of compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship throughout their life. Moreover, the abovementioned core values are the identity of all students who enrolled in FCIC. They are expected to carry with them these resources in their way of life as students, and until they are fully prepared to leave the portals of the institution for their professional practice. Further, FCIC ensures that these core values are embedded in the learner's curricular and co-curricular activities.

However, despite the integration of core values in FCIC, there were behavioral problems of Junior High school students reported by the teachers to the Guidance Office which contradict to the core values of the school. These behavioral problems include causing trouble

inside the classrooms, throwing trashes just anywhere, bullying other students specifically those who are weak and other behavioral problems. With this premise, the researcher was motivated to conduct the study as it would benefit the school administration, faculty, staff, students, and stakeholders as well. This study provides valuable insights into the extent to which Junior High School students practice the FCIC core values. By understanding these practices, school administration can identify areas of strength and opportunities for growth, enabling them to implement targeted interventions that not only deepen students' awareness of core values but also sustain their engagement over time. For faculty and staff, the findings can serve as a catalyst for re-aligning and integrating these core values into their pedagogical approaches. This could involve embedding core values into lesson plans, enhancing classroom activities, and enriching non-academic programs with value-driven initiatives. Such alignment not only fosters an interconnected school culture but also empowers educators to model and reinforce these values in various contexts, thereby promoting a holistic educational experience for students.

Research Questions

This study assessed the extent of the core value practices of the FCIC Junior high school students. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the respondent's level of awareness on the following FCIC Core Values?
 - 1.1 Compassion
 - 1.2 Excellence
 - 1.3 Integrity
 - 1.4 Peace
 - 1.5 Responsible Stewardship
2. What is the respondent's extent of practice on the following FCIC Core Values?
 - 1.6 Compassion
 - 1.7 Excellence
 - 1.8 Integrity
 - 1.9 Peace
 - 1.10 Responsible Stewardship
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practices of the Franciscan Core Values?
4. Is there a significant difference on the extent of practices among the Franciscan Core Values?
5. What can be proposed as the output of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed quantitative research, which involves the collection and analysis of numerical data to identify patterns, averages, relationships, and trends (Bhandari, 2020). This approach was chosen because it allows for objective measurement and statistical analysis of the respondents' level of awareness and extent of practice of the Franciscan Core Values.

Specifically, the study utilized descriptive research methods, using survey questionnaires to gather data on how well students recognize and apply these core values in their daily lives. By following a systematic approach, quantitative research enables the study to generate reliable and generalizable results, providing valuable insights into how students understand and integrate these values. Additionally, this method allows for comparisons, trend analysis, and the identification of potential areas for improvement, ultimately supporting efforts to strengthen value formation among students.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents, showing that 85 students participated in the survey, representing 30% of the total 282 Junior High School students enrolled at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. The study employed stratified simple random sampling; a method that ensures each subgroup within the population is proportionally represented. According to Wu (2024), simple random sampling is one of the most straightforward and effective techniques for selecting test inputs in research. By using this method, the researcher ensures that each student has an equal opportunity to be included in the study, reducing selection bias and increasing the reliability of the findings. Additionally, as noted by Thomas (2020), surveying students across different grade levels enhances the representativeness of the sample, ensuring that diverse perspectives and experiences regarding the Franciscan Core Values are accurately captured.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Grade Level	Number of students	Sample
Grade 7	76	23
Grade 8	57	17
Grade 9	61	18
Grade 10	88	27
	282	85

This study was conducted in the High School Department of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception (FCIC), located in Baybay City, Leyte, during Academic Year 2023-2024. FCIC is a private Catholic institution accredited by PAASCU and operates as a non-stock, non-profit organization. It is owned and administered by the Sisters of St. Francis of Perpetual Adoration, whose patron saints are Our Lady of the Immaculate Conception and Saint Francis of Assisi.

The school's seal reflects this dual patronage, featuring the Tau Cross of St. Francis and a sketch of the Blessed Virgin. As a Franciscan institution, FCIC upholds the charism of Blessed Maria Theresia Bonzel, OSF, who embraced the spirituality of Saint Francis of Assisi. Central to its educational philosophy are the five core values—compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship—which serve as the guiding principles in both academic and extracurricular activities. These values are deeply ingrained in the institution's mission to cultivate a holistic, faith-driven, and service-oriented learning environment.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire adapted from Values Education Books (Gonzales, 2013) to align with the research objectives. Prior permission was obtained from the publishing companies to incorporate the questionnaire found in the Values Education Textbooks. The questionnaire consisted of two main sections: Level of Awareness and Extent of Practice. The first section measured students' understanding of the FCIC core values—compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship—through ten statements for each value, with responses categorized using a four-point Likert scale: Fully aware (4), Moderately aware (3), Aware (2), and Not aware (1). The second section assessed the extent to which students applied these core values in their daily lives using a parallel set of ten statements per value, rated on a similar four-point scale: Always practice (4), Moderately practice (3), Fairly practice (2), and Not practice (1). The structured format of the questionnaire ensured comprehensive data collection, providing measurable insights into the relationship between students' awareness and their actual application of the Franciscan core values.

Gathering of Data

To collect the necessary data, the researcher followed a structured process to ensure the validity and reliability of the responses. A transmittal letter was first sent to the Dean of the Graduate School to obtain approval for conducting the study. Once approved, a formal letter of permission was submitted to the School Principal to authorize the distribution of the questionnaire. Before administering the final survey, a pretest was conducted with 10 randomly selected students from different grade levels to evaluate the clarity, relevance, and validity of the questionnaire items. The pretest results provided direct evidence of the instrument's effectiveness and helped refine any ambiguous items.

After validating the questionnaire, the final version was distributed to the target respondents through ARALINKS CLE (Collaborative Learning Environment), an online platform used by the school. The researcher posted the survey on ARALINKS CLE and

instructed students to complete it within a given timeframe. To ensure maximum participation, constant follow-ups were made through Messenger, reminding students to submit their responses. Over the course of one month, responses were systematically gathered. After a complete turnout of responses, the collected data were computed, analyzed, and interpreted to derive meaningful insights. The thorough data collection process ensured the accuracy and reliability of the findings while maximizing student participation.

To answer the level of awareness of the core values and extent of practices, mean scores more identified. The computed mean was categorized using the numerical and descriptive ratings for level of awareness and extent of practice indicated below.

Weighted Mean			Description	Interpretation
3.25	-	4.00	Fully Aware	Respondents show full knowledge of the core values
2.50	-	3.24	Moderately Aware	Respondents show moderate knowledge of the core values
1.75	-	2.49	Aware	Respondents show knowledge of the core values
1.0	-	1.74	Not Aware	Respondents does not show knowledge of the core values

As to the extent of practice, the category of means are as follows:

Weighted Mean			Description	Interpretation
3.25	-	4.00	Always Practice	Respondents were found to be always practiced
2.50	-	3.24	Moderately Practice	Respondents were found to be sometimes practiced
1.75	-	2.49	Fairly	Respondents were found to be rarely practiced
1.0	-	1.74	Not Practice	Respondents were never practiced

To get the relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practice, chi-square was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Awareness on Core Values

The respondents' level of awareness regarding the five FCIC Core Values—compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship—is presented in Tables 2.1 to 2.5.

Compassion

Compassion, as a core value, emphasizes reaching out to others in need, offering support to the less fortunate, and demonstrating kindness. The findings in Table 2.1 indicate that the respondents have a general awareness of compassion, with an overall mean score of 2.06, categorized as "aware." However, differences in awareness levels were observed across specific indicators.

Higher levels of awareness were recorded for indicators such as "Taking time to listen to others who need compassionate listening" and "Assisting in household chores." Conversely, lower awareness levels were noted for "Offering extra resources to the less fortunate" and "Distributing basic needs like food, clothes, water, and medicine." These results suggest that while students understand the concept of compassion, practical applications such as sharing resources require reinforcement. Supporting this, Carter (2019) asserts that compassion enhances social bonds and fosters positive interactions, which can ultimately improve academic and social outcomes.

Table 2.1 Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Core Value of Compassion

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Awareness
1. Taking time to listen to others who need compassionate listening.	2.20	Aware
2. Assisting in the household chores, such as washing the dishes and sweeping the floors.	2.18	Aware
3. Caring helping others on their endeavors.	2.13	Aware
4. Cheering people who are experiencing problems.	2.10	Aware
5. Helping others on their academic activities.	2.05	Aware
6. Entertaining others who are lowly with wholesome jokes.	2.03	Aware

7. Reaching out to others especially those in need.	2.01	Aware
8. Willing to be of service to others, and sensitive to their feelings.	1.99	Aware
9. Distributing basic needs like food, clothes, water, and medicine.	1.96	Aware
10. Offering extra resources to the less fortunate	1.96	Aware
Overall	2.06	Aware

As evidenced by the study's findings, the respondents feel that being attentive to those in need of sympathetic listening, evaluating how well they're doing home tasks like sweeping the floors and washing the dishes, and showing concern and support to others in their pursuits all demonstrate awareness. Conversely, delivering necessities like food, clothing, water, and medication and providing extra resources to the less fortunate, as well as being open to helping others and considerate of their feelings, demonstrates the awareness among others. This result is supported by Verdugo (2021) who offers an insight that the cornerstone of caring for others is looking after oneself. Since everyone may live in a sustainable environment thanks to nature. In support to this, being in the caring ministry is a vital role, as Ondrejko (2021) cite the importance of avoiding stress and exhaustion, practicing good time management, and observing self-care. Since being able to do these successfully is what brings about compassion satisfaction.

Excellence

Excellence, defined as striving for continuous improvement and maintaining high standards, was assessed across ten indicators. Table 2.2 shows an overall mean of 2.04, signifying "aware." The highest-rated indicators include "Expressing and appreciating others' good work" and "Trying new things, learning from best practices, and managing risks." However, students exhibited lower awareness in "Actively seeking feedback from teachers, staff, and parents," suggesting a need for greater emphasis on self-improvement and constructive criticism. De Kleijn (2021) emphasizes the importance of proactive feedback-seeking behavior as a critical factor in student growth and academic success.

Table 2.2. Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Core Values of Excellence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Awareness
1. Expressing and appreciating others' good work, and maintaining a positive attitude.	2.13	Aware

2. Trying new things, learning from best practices, and managing risks.	2.10	Aware
3. Asking and researching for correct information in matters that I lack knowledge	2.08	Aware
4. Continuously improving processes to eliminate errors, create value, and enhance quality.	2.08	Aware
5. Exhibiting passion and positivity in aspiring for achievement.	2.07	Aware
6. Proving excellence in academics through collaboration with other students.	2.05	Aware
7. Demonstrating excellence in finding innovative solutions to problems.	2.03	Aware
8. Setting and achieving high standards for one's performance and ambitious goals for one's future.	1.99	Aware
9. Listening to the voice of those in authority and finding ways to meet and exceed their needs.	1.96	Aware
10. Actively seeking feedback from teachers, staff, and parents, and use these to improve one's performance.	1.95	Aware
Overall	2.04	Aware

Integrity

Integrity involves honesty, accountability, and ethical behavior. As reflected in Table 2.3, the respondents demonstrated awareness of integrity, with an overall mean of 2.07. The highest awareness was recorded for "Trusting and respecting fellow students, teachers, staff, and parents," reinforcing the idea that students value trust and respect in relationships. However, the lowest-rated indicator, "Treating others equally without self-interest or prejudice," suggests challenges in fostering fairness and inclusivity. Begeny (2021) highlights those interactions within groups provide opportunities to demonstrate fairness and appreciate diversity, which should be reinforced in educational settings.

Table 2.3 Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Core Value of Integrity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Awareness
1. Trusting and respecting fellow students, teachers, staff, and parents.	2.17	Aware
2. Using data and facts to inform one's decisions, and are honest about one's biases.	2.12	Aware
3. Submitting original work and completing individual assessments independently.	2.11	Aware
4. Seeking help if struggling or not sure of expectation problems.	2.09	Aware
5. Speaking and acting truthfully.	2.07	Aware
6. Maintaining confidences, especially confidential information.	2.07	Aware
7. Doing what is saying well, and keeping the word of honor.	2.07	Aware
8. Following instructor's guidelines and expectations for assignments and tests.	2.05	Aware
9. Setting good examples and mentoring others.	1.98	Aware
10. Treating others equally without self-interests or prejudice.	1.97	Aware
Overall	2.07	Aware

Peace

The assessment of peace, as shown in Table 2.4, resulted in an overall mean of 2.10, categorized as "aware." The highest-rated indicator, "Sowing love to everyone: family, friends, schoolmates, teachers, and staff," suggests that students recognize the importance of positive relationships. However, "Consoling those in need by making oneself available" received the lowest rating, indicating a potential gap in students' willingness to offer emotional support. Smith (2024) asserts that being present for others in times of need fosters emotional well-being and social cohesion.

Table 2.4 Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Awareness on the Core Value of Peace

Indicators	Weigh ted Mean	Level of Aware ness
1. Sowing love to everyone: family, friends, schoolmates, teachers, and staff.	2.19	Aware
2. Demonstrating strong faith in God.	2.17	Aware
3. Encouraging others to be hopeful in times of despair.	2.17	Aware
4. Loving others unconditionally.	2.12	Aware
5. Forgiving those who caused injury physically, mentally, emotionally as well.	2.11	Aware
6. Manifesting joy amidst sadness by cheering oneself and others	2.08	Aware
7. Giving time, and talent freely.	2.07	Aware
8. Giving light to others by sharing resources material or non-material.	2.07	Aware
9. Understanding the weaknesses of oneself and others through giving tutorials in academic works.	2.05	Aware
10. Consoling those in need by making oneself available.	2.04	Aware
Overall	2.10	Aware

Stewardship On God's Creation

Responsible stewardship is the fifth core value in the study. Exercising responsible stewardship is caring for the gifts God has given, including the environment, own personal talents and others resources.

This entails caring for the environment and managing resources wisely. Table 2.5 indicates an overall mean of 2.08, signifying "aware." The highest-rated indicators, "Caring for God's creation" and "Observing health protocols that benefit the well-being of everyone," suggest a strong sense of environmental responsibility. However, "Breaking plastic habits by participating in the community's 'No Plastic Day'" received the lowest score, implying that sustainability practices require further reinforcement. Gamaralalage (2023) stresses the need for educational initiatives that instill sustainable habits among students.

Table 2.5 Distribution of the Respondents’ Level of Awareness on the Core Value of Responsible Stewardship

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Awareness
1. Caring for God’s creation.	2.19	Aware
2. Observing health protocol that benefits the wellbeing of everyone.	2.19	Aware
3. Observing the community environment protection practices.	2.14	Aware
4. Saving energy by being mindful of the use of electricity and other electronic devices.	2.11	Aware
5. Observing self-care habits to keep oneself healthy.	2.10	Aware
6. Promoting peace and justice to all through my knowledge of the Catholic teaching.	2.06	Aware
7. Practicing food waste reduction by using a water bottle instead of a plastic container, glass jars, and containers for food.	2.04	Aware
8. Disseminating and sharing to others the environmental issues learned from the environmental programs.	2.00	Aw
9. Sharing the available to all.	2.00	are
10. Breaking plastic habits by participating in the community’s “No plastic Day.”	1.98	Aw
		are
		Aware
Overall	2.08	Aware

Summary of the Level of Awareness on the Core Values

The overall average mean score of 2.07 indicates that the respondents are generally aware of the FCIC core values. While knowledge of these values exists, practical applications vary. Awareness fosters positive behavior, enhances academic growth, and promotes a supportive environment. However, areas requiring improvement include encouraging fairness,

fostering emotional support, and reinforcing sustainability efforts. Wiśniewska (2023) underscores that instilling values in students is a crucial responsibility of educators, emphasizing the need for continued reinforcement through curricular and co-curricular activities.

Table 2.6. Summary of the Level of Awareness on the Core Values

Core Values	Weighted Mean	Description
Compassion	2.06	Aware
Excellence	2.04	Aware
Integrity	2.07	Aware
Peace	2.10	Aware
Responsible Stewardship	2.08	Aware
Average	2.07	Aware

Extent of Practice on Core Values

The extent to which the respondents practice the FCIC core values is presented in Tables 3.1 to 3.5.

Compassion

This study assesses the extent to which respondents practice compassion. In this study, compassion is defined as the act of reaching out to others, particularly the less fortunate, by freely sharing one's time, talent, and resources. The results indicate that the overall practice of compassion among respondents has a mean score of 1.92, suggesting that they demonstrate this core value to a fair extent.

Among the indicators, *"Taking time to listen to others who need compassionate listening"* received the highest mean score of 2.07. This finding suggests that respondents highly value the act of listening as a form of compassion. It highlights the importance of being present for others, acknowledging their feelings, and offering emotional support. This result implies that respondents have a compassionate heart, as they recognize the significance of active listening in fostering stronger relationships. By focusing on developing listening skills, they contribute to the emotional well-being of others and create an environment where people feel safe to express their emotions. This finding aligns with Galan (2021), who asserts that providing compassionate care is a fundamental component of delivering high-quality support.

Conversely, the indicator *"Offering extra resources to the less fortunate"* received the lowest mean score of 1.71. This suggests that although respondents exhibit empathy toward those in

need, they do not consistently take the initiative to provide material assistance. The lower emphasis on financial or material support may indicate that respondents prioritize emotional support or active listening over tangible aid. Additionally, this result may reflect challenges in resource allocation or a perception that simply providing material assistance is not a sufficient solution to deeper social issues. This finding highlights the need for a broader understanding of compassion—one that encompasses not only material support but also emotional and social dimensions in assisting the less fortunate.

Furthermore, Lonczak (2019) emphasizes that compassion is a powerful motivator for courageous and constructive actions that benefit both individuals and the community. However, compassion does not always emerge automatically in response to another person's suffering. Rather, it develops when individuals perceive a situation as severe, unjust, or personally relatable. This insight underscores the complexity of compassionate behavior and suggests that fostering a deeper awareness of various forms of compassion may encourage more proactive efforts in supporting those in need.

Table 3.1 Distribution of the Respondents' Extent of Practice on the Core Value of Compassion

Indicators	Weigh ted Mea n	Exten t of Pract ice
1. I take time to listen to others who need compassionate listening.	2.07	Fairly Practice
2. I do household chores, such as washing the dishes and sweeping the floors.	2.03	Fairly Practice
3. I help others on their academic activities.	1.99	Fairly Practice
4. I reach out to others especially those in need.	1.98	Fairly Practice
5. I care and help others in their endeavors.	1.96	Fairly Practice
6. I am willing to be of service to others, and sensitive to their feelings.	1.93	Fairly Practice
7. I cheer people who are experiencing problems.	1.92	Fairly Practice
8. I entertain others who are lowly with whole some jokes.	1.88	Fairly Practice
9. I distribute basic needs like food, clothes, water, and medicine.	1.75	Fairly Practice
10. I offer extra resources to the less fortunate.	1.71	Not Practice

Overall	1.92	Fairly Practice
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Excellence

The concept of excellence emphasizes maximizing resources, talents, and skills to achieve the best possible outcomes, ultimately leading to sustainable results. This study assesses the extent to which respondents practice the core value of excellence. The findings reveal that the respondents rarely practice excellence, with an overall mean score of 2.11. This suggests that while they acknowledge the importance of utilizing their resources, talents, and skills, they do not consistently maximize them to achieve the best sustainable outcomes.

Among the indicators, *"Expressing and appreciating others' good work and maintaining a positive attitude"* received the highest mean score of 2.20, indicating a fair level of practice. This finding reflects a recognition of the importance of valuing others' efforts and fostering a positive mindset, which are essential in promoting excellence. A supportive and appreciative environment enhances performance by encouraging collaboration and motivating individuals to strive for higher standards. When appreciation and encouragement are emphasized, people are more likely to feel valued, leading to a culture where excellence is nurtured.

Conversely, the indicator *"Actively seeking feedback from teachers, staff, and parents and using it to improve one's performance"* received the lowest mean score among the ten indicators. This suggests that respondents may struggle with handling criticism and feedback, possibly due to a lack of confidence or knowledge in processing constructive input. Additionally, the low score may indicate a limited willingness to collaborate or form alliances with others for continuous improvement. According to Stone and Heen (2019), developing the ability to provide and accept constructive criticism is crucial for both professional and personal growth. Effectively utilizing feedback fosters self-improvement, strengthens skills, and enhances overall performance. Engaging in self-reflection exercises can help individuals become more aware of their responses to feedback, recognize their areas for growth, and apply newly acquired knowledge to real-world actions. By integrating feedback into practice, individuals can develop habits that promote continuous improvement and long-term excellence.

These findings highlight the need for greater emphasis on cultivating a mindset that embraces feedback as a tool for self-improvement. Encouraging individuals to seek and apply feedback constructively can significantly enhance their ability to maximize their potential, ultimately fostering a culture of excellence.

Table 3.2 Distribution of the Respondents' Extent of Practice on the Core Value of Excellence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Extent of Practice
1. I express and appreciate others' good work, and maintain a positive attitude.	2.20	Fairly Practice
2. I ask and research for correct information in matters that I lack the knowledge.	2.16	Fairly Practice
3. I continuously improve processes to eliminate errors, create value, and enhance quality.	2.12	Fairly Practice
4. I set and achieve high standards for my performance and ambitious goals for my future.	2.11	Fairly Practice
5. I prove excellence in academics through collaboration with other students.	2.10	Fairly Practice
6. I demonstrate excellence in finding innovative solutions to problems.	2.10	Fairly Practice
7. I try new things, learn from best practices, and manage risks.	2.10	Fairly Practice
8. I listen to the voice of those in authority and find ways to meet and exceed their needs.	2.10	Fairly Practice
9. I exhibit passion and positivity in aspiring for achievement.	2.07	Fairly Practice
10. I actively seek feedback from teachers, staff, and parents, and use these to improve one's performance.	2.05	Fairly Practice
Overall	2.11	Fairly Practice

Integrity

The extent to which respondents practice integrity is measured in this study. Integrity is defined as the consistency between what individuals say and do, emphasizing the alignment of actions with words. True integrity involves honesty, reliability, and ethical behavior in both communication and actions.

The overall mean score of 2.15 indicates that respondents *fairly practice* the core value of integrity. This suggests that while they acknowledge the importance of integrity, their consistency in upholding it varies. The findings highlight the crucial role of integrity in shaping personal character and fostering a strong sense of accountability within educational settings. Respondents recognize that integrity contributes to a positive learning environment by reinforcing trust, responsibility, and ethical decision-making.

Among the indicators, *"Following instructions, guidelines, and expectations for assignments and tests"* received the highest mean score of 2.22. This suggests that respondents find it easier to adhere to established rules and guidelines, acknowledging that compliance fosters a sense of responsibility. Their adherence to academic expectations reflects an understanding that integrity is closely linked to accountability and ethical conduct. As Wong (2024) emphasizes, acting ethically and transparently means prioritizing what is right over personal gain, demonstrating accountability, and maintaining ethical behavior even when unobserved.

Conversely, the indicator *"Speaking and acting honestly"* received the lowest mean score among the ten indicators. This finding suggests that respondents may struggle with openly expressing the truth in certain situations, possibly due to fear of consequences, social pressure, or uncertainty about how honesty will be received. Armand (2020) argues that telling the truth is not always easy, but it provides an opportunity to practice and reinforce the value of honesty—a fundamental pillar of integrity. This suggests that fostering a culture that encourages open and honest communication is essential in strengthening integrity among individuals.

Overall, these findings underscore the importance of reinforcing integrity not only in rule-following but also in the practice of honesty and transparency. Encouraging individuals to consistently align their words with their actions can help develop stronger ethical standards, ultimately contributing to a more principled and trustworthy community.

Table 3.3 Distribution of the Respondents’ Extent of Practice on the Core Value of Integrity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Extent of Practice
1. I follow instructions, guidelines, and expectations for assignments and tests.	2.22	Fairly Practice
2. I trust and respect fellow students, teachers, staff, and parents.	2.21	Fairly Practice
3. I treat others equally without self-interest or prejudice.	2.17	Fairly Practice
4. I do what I say well, and keep the word	2.17	Fairly Practice

of honor.		
5. I submit original work and complete individual assessments independently.	2.17	Fairly Practice
6. I maintain confidence, especially in confidential information.	2.14	Fairly Practice
7. I seek help if am struggling or am not sure of expectations.	2.14	Fairly Practice
8. I set good examples and mentor others.	2.13	Fairly Practice
9. I use data and facts to inform my decisions and am honest about one's biases.	2.09	Fairly Practice
10. I speak and act truthfully.	2.08	Fairly Practice
Overall	2.15	Fairly Practice

The capacity of students to foster healthy relationships and live harmoniously with others is an essential aspect of the core value of peace. In this study, the overall mean score for the extent of practicing peace is 2.16, indicating that respondents *fairly practice* this core value. This suggests that they demonstrate efforts in building respectful relationships, promoting understanding, and fostering cooperation in their daily interactions.

The findings imply that respondents have the ability to embrace and actively practice peace, contributing to an environment that nurtures mutual understanding and social harmony. Their ability to engage in peaceful interactions suggests a recognition of the importance of maintaining positive relationships, which ultimately leads to a more cohesive and cooperative society.

In support of this, Pace (2023) highlights that embracing harmony in relationships is transformative and requires patience, positive communication, and an appreciation of individual uniqueness. Maintaining peaceful relationships demands continuous effort, including fostering greater understanding, cultivating joy, and strengthening interpersonal bonds. These insights emphasize that peace is not merely the absence of conflict but a proactive commitment to nurturing relationships through empathy, respect, and open communication.

By further reinforcing the value of peace, individuals can contribute to a more harmonious community where mutual respect and cooperation thrive. Encouraging the practice of active listening, conflict resolution, and empathy can enhance the ability of individuals to sustain peaceful interactions, ultimately strengthening social cohesion.

Table 3.4 Distribution of the Respondents' Extent of Practice on the Core Value of Peace

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Extent of Practice
1. I sow love to everyone: family, friends, schoolmates, teachers, and staff.	2.25	Fairly Practice
2. I encourage others to be hopeful in times of despair.	2.24	Fairly Practice
3. I demonstrate strong faith in God.	2.23	Fairly Practice
4. I console those in need by making myself available.	2.18	Fairly Practice
5. I give time, and talent freely.	2.17	Fairly Practice
6. I manifest joy amidst sadness by cheering myself and others	2.15	Fairly Practice
7. I give light to others by sharing resources material or non-material.	2.14	Fairly Practice
8. I love others unconditionally.	2.12	Fairly Practice
9. I understand the weaknesses of myself and others through giving tutorials in academic works.	2.11	Fairly
10. I forgive those who caused me injury physically, mentally, emotionally as well.	2.07	Practice
		Fairly
		Practice
Overall	2.16	Fairly Practice

Among the indicators assessed, the respondents demonstrated the highest level of practice in *"sowing love to everyone, including family, friends, schoolmates, and staff."* This suggests that they actively express care and kindness in their relationships, reinforcing a sense of unity and mutual respect. However, the lowest-scoring indicator was *"forgiving someone who hurt them physically, psychologically, or emotionally,"* indicating that respondents struggle with forgiveness, particularly in situations where they have experienced harm.

This finding aligns with Litner (2020), who explains that forgiveness is often misunderstood, making it difficult to practice. Many perceive forgiveness as excusing or condoning wrongdoing, but in reality, it serves as a means of emotional healing. Letting go of resentment allows individuals to move forward with a lighter heart, ultimately freeing themselves from the burden of past hurt. Furthermore, forgiveness can facilitate relationship reconciliation by helping both the injured party and the one who caused harm recognize the impact of their actions.

Wilkinson (2000) further emphasizes that forgiveness is a process of releasing grudges and resentment, which is essential for achieving personal peace and emotional well-being. He highlights that forgiving oneself and others fosters healing on both emotional and spiritual levels. Accepting forgiveness as a transformative process enables individuals to free themselves from the negative consequences of past experiences, ultimately leading to inner peace and personal growth.

These findings suggest the need for a deeper understanding of forgiveness, not as a sign of weakness but as a powerful tool for emotional resilience and healing. Encouraging individuals to view forgiveness as a means of personal liberation rather than an obligation can help cultivate a culture of peace and emotional well-being within communities.

Responsible Stewardship

Responsible stewardship refers to being accountable for managing human, financial, and natural resources wisely. In this study, the overall mean score of 2.19 indicates that the extent to which respondents practice responsible stewardship is classified as *"fairly practiced."* This suggests that while respondents recognize the importance of accountability, their actual engagement in responsible stewardship remains limited. The findings highlight the need to strengthen awareness and commitment to responsible management of resources to ensure sustainability and ethical responsibility. Steward (2022) emphasizes that an effective steward demonstrates mindfulness and a strong sense of accountability in managing resources, recognizing them as entrusted responsibilities that require careful oversight.

Among the indicators assessed, *"Taking part in the community's 'No Plastic Day'"* received the lowest ranking, indicating that participation in this initiative is only *fairly practiced*. This suggests that respondents may still struggle with reducing their plastic use, and there may be limited awareness or engagement in environmental activities. The low participation could reflect a lack of urgency or prioritization when it comes to environmental stewardship.

This finding aligns with Vasquez (2024), who underscores the importance of advocacy and awareness in addressing plastic pollution. He argues that individuals and communities must actively use their voices to promote sustainable practices and support businesses that reduce single-use plastics in their supply chains. Without continued advocacy, initiatives like "No Plastic Day" may struggle to gain widespread adoption. Additionally, Parker (2019) highlights that plastic pollution has become one of the most pressing yet frequently overlooked environmental issues. The reluctance to adopt sustainable habits can contribute to long-term ecological harm, underscoring the need for more proactive efforts in reducing plastic waste.

These insights suggest that strengthening responsible stewardship requires targeted efforts in education, advocacy, and community engagement. Encouraging individuals to actively participate in sustainability initiatives, reinforcing the impact of small actions, and fostering a culture of environmental responsibility can help promote more effective stewardship practices. By doing so, communities can work towards a more sustainable and accountable management of resources.

Table 3.5 Distribution of the Respondents’ Extent of Practice on the Core Value of Responsible Stewardship

Indicators	Weigh ted Mea n	Exten t of Pract ice
1. I promote peace and justice to all through my knowledge of Catholic Social Teaching.	2.24	Fairly Practice
2. I observe the community environment protection practices.	2.24	Fairly Practice
3. I care for God’s creation.	2.21	Fairly Practice
4. I observe health protocol that benefits the well-being of everyone.	2.21	Fairly Practice
5. I practice food waste reduction by using a water bottle instead of a plastic container, glass jars, and containers for food.	2.21	Fairly Practice
6. I observe self-care habits to keep oneself healthy.	2.20	Fairly Practice
7. I share my available resources to all.	2.18	Fairly Practice
8. I disseminate and share to others the environmental issues learned from the environmental programs.	2.17	Fairly Practice
9. I save energy by being mindful of the use of electricity and other electronic devices.	2.16	Fairly Practice
10. I break plastic habits by participating in the community’s “No plastic Day”.	2.09	Fairly Practice
Overall	2.19	Fairly Practice

Table 3.6 Summary of the Extent of Practice

Core Values	Weighted Mean	Description
Compassion	1.92	Fairly Practice
Excellence	2.11	Fairly Practice
Integrity	2.15	Fairly Practice
Peace	2.16	Fairly Practice
Responsible Stewardship	2.19	Fairly Practice
Average	2.10	Fairly Practice

As reflected in Table 5, the overall average weighted mean of 2.10 indicates that the five core values are *fairly practiced* by the respondents. Among these, responsible stewardship received the highest weighted mean of 2.19, suggesting that this core value is the most practiced. This aligns with the respondents' level of awareness, affirming that they recognize their responsibility in caring for human, financial, and natural resources as part of their stewardship role. This finding highlights that students acknowledge the importance of managing these resources wisely, as part of their duty to protect and sustain God's creation. Drain (2019) supports this notion, emphasizing that stewardship is fundamentally about taking care of the resources entrusted to us and actively working to preserve the environment.

On the other hand, compassion received the lowest weighted mean of 1.92, though still categorized as *fairly practiced*. Compassion, as defined in this study, refers to reaching out to others, particularly the less fortunate, by freely sharing one's time, talent, and resources. While respondents demonstrate some level of compassion, its lower ranking suggests that tangible acts of kindness and generosity may not be fully integrated into their daily lives. This finding implies that while students may feel empathy for those in need, there is a gap between feeling compassion and taking meaningful action to support others.

Furthermore, this result underscores the need to foster a culture of giving and support that strengthens interpersonal connections and encourages deeper engagement in acts of service. True compassion extends beyond sympathy; it involves a conscious effort to alleviate suffering through intentional action. Struckmeyer (2019) reinforces this perspective, asserting that acts of compassion, generosity, service, and justice not only benefit others but also shape individuals into better, more empathetic people.

These findings suggest that while responsible stewardship is relatively well-practiced, there is a need for greater emphasis on cultivating and embedding compassion into students' daily actions. Encouraging a mindset of service, promoting active involvement in charitable initiatives, and reinforcing the transformative power of compassion can help bridge the gap between awareness and meaningful engagement in helping others.

A Significant Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and the Extent of Practice

Table 4. Relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practices of the Franciscan Core Values

Franciscan Core Values	Chi-Square Value	Df	p-value	Significance
Compassion	47.555	4	.000	Significant
Excellence	61.563 ^a	4	.000	Significant
Integrity	39.173 ^a	4	.000	Significant
Peace	40.491 ^a	2	.000	Significant
Responsible Stewardship	52.973^a	2	.000	Significant

The computed Pearson Chi-Square values indicate a significant relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practice of the core values: compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship. This statistical significance suggests that the respondents' level of awareness directly influences how they embody these values in their daily lives.

For compassion, the computed chi-square value of 47.555 (df = 4, p-value = 0.00) signifies a strong correlation between awareness and practice. Similarly, for excellence, the computed chi-square value of 61.563 (df = 4, p-value = 0.00) underscores the importance of awareness in fostering a commitment to high standards. In integrity, a chi-square value of 39.173 (df = 4, p-value = 0.00) suggests that recognizing the significance of honesty and ethical behavior increases its application in real-life scenarios. For peace, a chi-square value of 40.664 (df = 2, p-value = 0.00) implies that understanding the value of harmonious relationships enhances peaceful interactions. Lastly, for responsible stewardship, the chi-square value of 53.973 (df = 2, p-value = 0.00) highlights the link between awareness and accountability in managing resources.

Additionally, the p-value test at the 0.00 significance level confirmed that all computed p-values were lower than the set significance threshold (p-value < α ; 0.001 < 0.01), reinforcing the validity of the findings. A low p-value indicates that the observed relationships are statistically significant and unlikely due to chance.

These findings suggest that awareness of core values plays a pivotal role in shaping behavior. As seen in Tables 2a–e and Tables 3a–e, students who exhibit higher awareness of these values are more inclined to practice them. This result underscores the fundamental role of academic institutions in instilling and reinforcing values through education and school culture. Gallinero et al. (2018) affirm that educational institutions have a primary mandate to

promote values through instruction, guidance, and role modeling by administrators, faculty, and staff. Furthermore, they emphasize that values are better caught than taught, meaning that students internalize and practice values more effectively when they are consistently demonstrated in their learning environment.

This study highlights the necessity for institutions to actively integrate core values into academic and extracurricular activities, ensuring that students not only understand these values but also apply them in meaningful ways. The findings advocate for a holistic approach to values education, where awareness, reinforcement, and real-world application work together to foster responsible, ethical, and compassionate individuals.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Practice Among the Franciscan Core Values

The analysis presented in Table 7 reveals that respondents exhibit varying degrees of adherence to the core values. The data show that the distribution of students who always practice the core values is equal to those who moderately practice them, suggesting that while many students consistently uphold these values, an equally large group demonstrates only partial commitment. Additionally, the number of students who fairly practice or do not practice the core values is notably low, indicating that while most respondents engage with these principles, a small fraction struggles to fully integrate them into their daily lives. This finding highlights the need for targeted initiatives to reinforce value formation, ensuring that all students—not just the majority—develop a deeper and more consistent application of the Franciscan core values.

Table 5. Differences on the extent of practices among the Franciscan Core Values

Core Values	EXTENT OF PRACTICE (<i>Total Frequency</i>)				TOTAL
	4 (Always Practice)	3 (Moderately Practice)	2 (Fairly Practice)	1 (Not Practice)	
Compassion	352	352	145	17	866
Excellence	326	326	132	17	801
Integrity	355	355	127	8	845
Peace	389	389	130	15	923
Responsible Stewardship	395	395	113	10	913
Total	1817	1817	647	67	4348

Chi-Square Value ($df=12$) = 15.585^{ns}, *p-value* = .221, ^{ns}Not Significant

A closer analysis of Table 7 reveals that while the majority of students consistently practice the core values, the 647 responses for "fairly practiced" and 67 for "not practiced" remain a concern. Even though these numbers are relatively small, they still have the potential to impact the school's overall image and influence the attitudes and behaviors of other students in the junior high school population.

Douglas et al. (2016) emphasize that disruptive behavior is a persistent issue, and if left unaddressed, it tends to continue and spread. This suggests that students who only fairly practice or do not practice core values may inadvertently set a precedent for others, reinforcing behaviors that contradict the school's foundational principles.

Furthermore, as seen in Appendix E, the cross-tabulated data highlight significant differences in how core values are practiced. For instance, peace has an expected count of 389 under "fairly practiced," while responsible stewardship has an expected count of 395 under "always practiced." Meanwhile, the values categorized under "moderately aware" include compassion (352), excellence (326), and integrity (355). Notably, compassion also has an expected count of 352 under "fairly practiced," indicating that this value, in particular, may require further reinforcement.

The variations in expected counts, as reflected in Table 5, confirm that there are significant differences in the extent of core value practices among students. These disparities suggest a need for targeted interventions, such as structured value integration programs, student mentoring, and reinforcement activities, to bridge the gap between awareness and consistent practice. By addressing these differences proactively, the institution can further strengthen its core values and ensure that all students embody them in both thought and action.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that students are aware of the fundamental values of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception (FCIC), and this awareness may have contributed to the school's progress in both academic and extracurricular activities. However, while students demonstrate a basic understanding and practice of the Franciscan core values—compassion, excellence, integrity, peace, and responsible stewardship—their application remains insufficiently developed. Many students lack a deep, practical understanding of these values and how to effectively demonstrate them in their daily lives.

Moreover, the study highlights that a lack of role models may contribute to inconsistent practice of these values among students. Without visible examples of individuals consistently embodying these principles, some students may struggle to apply them in real-world situations. To bridge this gap, it is crucial to integrate these values not only in academics but also in extracurricular activities, ensuring that students have opportunities to internalize and live out these values in both structured and informal settings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following measures are recommended to strengthen the integration and practice of the Franciscan core values among students:

1. Deepen the integration of core values across all subjects and school services to provide students with consistent and meaningful experiences that reinforce the importance of these values in different contexts.
2. Intensify activities that promote the core values among students through targeted initiatives, such as:
3. Celebrating Values Education Month by organizing activities that focus on deepening students' value formation and encouraging self-reflection on their actions.
4. Expanding the celebration of St. Francis to incorporate interactive and experiential learning about the Franciscan core values, ensuring that students actively engage with these principles in a meaningful way.
5. Conducting seminars on Values and Moral Education to provide students with practical guidance and motivation to apply the core values in their daily lives, reinforcing the importance of character formation and ethical decision-making.
6. Adopt the proposed activity plan to enhance students' engagement with the Franciscan core values through structured programs that encourage consistent practice and reflection.

By implementing these recommendations, the institution can reinforce the Franciscan core values in both academic and extracurricular settings, ensuring that students not only understand these principles but also develop the ability to embody and apply them in their daily interactions and decision-making processes.

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